

KNITTED REINFORCED COMPOSITES - EFFECTS IN KNITTING STRUCTURE ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES -

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents bending and damping properties of 2.5 dimensional warp knitted fabric reinforced rigid epoxy and flexible epoxy resin composites. The knitted structural composites are anisotropic in nature. It is difficult to obtain superior bending stiffness and excellent damping property with the single rigid or flexible matrix composites. The hybrid of rigid and flexible matrix composite can be tailored to possess both relatively superior bending stiffness and excellent damping property.

KEYWORDS: 2.5 dimensional knitted fabric, bending properties, rigid resin, flexible resin, hybrid, loss factor.

1. INTRODUCTION

To compare with the conventional composite materials, textile structural composites play an important role in significantly improving the inter- and intra-laminar strength, feasibility of complex structural formation and in reducing cost during large-scale manufacturing¹⁾. Knitted fabrics possess not only the high productivity but also the superior conformability to the complicated shape due to the high deformability originated from the characteristic knitted structure²⁾. When we consider resin transfer molding (RTM) which is usually recognized as a mass production fabrication system, a preform process is required. The reinforcement is preshaped, which may be cut into pieces and placed into mold as a unit preform to fit the required geometrical shape, or which may be fabricated to get the shape by textile-preform-manufacturing technology. In spite of resin transfer molding

offering high potential in fabrication of large composite parts, the preform process might be an obstacle from cost efficiency. By utilizing knitted fabrics, the reinforcement can be deformed to fit the mold without the procedure of preform. This is one of the applications that emphasizes the unique feature of knitted fabric reinforcement.

Based on the loop formation direction in knitting, knitted fabrics can be classified into weft knit and warp knit. The authors have carried out a research program on investigation of knitted structural composites. The mechanical properties of fundamental weft³⁾ and warp^{4,5)} knitted fabric reinforced composites have been studied. In order to improve the through-thickness and inter-laminar strength and reduce the labour intensive fibre lay-up operations used in the fabrication, a new kind of three dimensional warp knitted fabric reinforced composite was fabricated. The bending and damping properties of single rigid and flexible matrix composites and hybrid matrix composites are discussed.

2. 2.5 DIMENSIONAL WARP KNIT (2.5DWK)

Aramid fibers (Technora, T-240, Teijin Co.) were warp knitted on a double needle bar raschel knitting machine (RM DU-6, Karl Mayer Co.) to produce double faced warp knitted fabrics by using five reeds. Figure 1(a) shows the back half structure of the face layer in the warp knitted fabric. Two reeds each were used to produce the layer of back half. One reed was used to stitch together the two layers of back half structures with a joint fiber bundle, as shown in Figure 1(b). Since the joint fiber bundle is perpendicular to the plane of face layer, thicker knitted fabrics can be easily produced. Figure 1(c) shows the actual section of the fabric. In the current study the fibre content in the thickness direction of the fabric is less compared to the fibre content in the planar direction. Hence, this special knitted fabric is defined as 2.5 dimensional warp knit (2.5DWK) in this paper.

Fig.1 Warp knitted structures produced by a double bar raschel machine.
(a) face structure of 2.5 dimensional warp knitted fabric, back half
(b) schematic diagram of 2.5 dimensional warp knitted fabric with face structure back half.
(c) actual section of a 2.5 dimensional warp knitted fabric.

3. EXPERIMENT

3.1 Materials and Sample Preparation

Two kinds of resin matrix were used in the experiment. One is the conventional epoxy resin (Epikote 828, Yuka Shell Co., Ltd) called as rigid resin. The other is the modified epoxy resin (KR 550, Koei Co., Ltd) called as flexible resin. The reinforcement used was the 2.5DWK mentioned above. The composite panels reinforced with single layer of the 2.5DWK fabric were made by hand lay-up method. A post curing treatment at 100°C for three hours was performed to obtain optimum mechanical properties. Three types of specimens were prepared; 1) the 2.5DWK fabric reinforced composite with rigid epoxy resin matrix (Type R), 2) the 2.5DWK fabric reinforced composite with flexible epoxy resin matrix (Type F) and 3) the 2.5DWK fabric reinforced composite with hybrid of rigid and flexible resin matrixes (Type RF or Type FR). Hybrid matrix composites were made by placing 2.5DWK fabric on a layer of rigid epoxy resin and later flexible epoxy resin was poured. Neat rigid and flexible epoxy resin specimens were also prepared. Specimens of 70 mm length, 15 mm width and 4 mm thickness were cut parallel to the course (C) and wale (W) direction of the 2.5DWK fabric.

3.2 Testing

Three point bending tests were conducted using an universal testing machine (Instron 4206) with a cross-head speed of 1.0 mm/min at room temperature. In particular, two kinds of bending tests were performed with the hybrid matrix composite: 1) the rigid resin was arranged at compression side of the specimen defined as Type RF, 2) the flexible side was arranged at the compression side of the specimen defined as Type FR. After the bending test, the specimens were polished for optical microscopy using standard metallographic techniques.

The vibration damping tests were also performed. Figure 2 shows the block diagram of measurement in a damping test. The testing specimen of 200 mm length, 15 mm width was clamped at one end and the free end oscillated sine wave vibration to resonate the specimen with sweeping frequency. From the resonant curve, the loss factor d can be given by $d = \Delta f / f$, where f is the natural frequency, Δf is the band width 3dB down from the top of the resonance curve.

Fig.2 Block diagram of complex modulus apparatus.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Single Matrix Composites

Figure 3 shows the bending stress-displacement curves of neat rigid and flexible epoxy resin. The rigid epoxy resin displayed brittle fracture behaviour. However, the flexible epoxy resin showed ductile behaviour and never fractured during the bending test. It can be noted that bending strength of the rigid epoxy resin is much higher than the flexible one. Figure 4 illustrates the bending stress-displacement curves of the wale and course direction in 2.5DWK fabric reinforced composites Type R and Type F. Irrespective of the wale and course directions, brittle fracture occurred at the ultimate point for all Type R specimens (see Type R-W and Type R-C in Fig.3). In the case of Type R, higher bending modulus, stiffness and strength are shown in the wale direction compared to that in the course direction (see Table 1). Unlike the rigid composite Type R, all Type F specimens did not fracture during bending test. The modulus, stiffness and strength of Type F are much smaller than those of Type R for both the wale and course directions. However, their values are relatively bigger compared to the neat flexible epoxy resin.

Fig.3 Bending stress-displacement curves of rigid epoxy resin and flexible epoxy resin.

Fig.4 Bending stress-displacement curves of Type R and Type F in both the course and wale direction.

Table 1 Bending properties of single matrix composites.

Type	Bending Modulus (GPa)		Bending Strength (MPa)		Bending Stiffness ($\times 10^{-3} \text{Nm}^2$)	
	C	W	C	W	C	W
R	3.51	5.62	77.92	184.49	268.40	463.95
F	0.02	0.04	1.63	2.17	1.03	2.42

Figure 5 shows the schematic diagram of bend tested Type R specimen. It can be noted that the cracks initiated from the tensile side of the specimen and grew in the thickness direction, resulting in the ultimate fracture. In the Type F tested specimen, no evidence of cracks could be observed from optical studies. The difference between Type R and Type F originated from the two kinds of epoxy resin resulted in different load transferring mechanisms within the composites and hence brittle and ductile behaviour. In the case of Type R, major amount of bending load is transferred to the reinforced fibers and hence superior stiffness and strength. The rigid resin can deform less compared to the knitted fabric reinforcement, resulting in resin cracks observed on the tensile side of the specimen. In the case of Type F, though the flexible matrix resin and knitted fabric were deforming under bending load, few reinforcing fibers were stretched, which resulted in lower stiffness and strength. The difference between the wale and course direction in Type R is mainly attributed to the inherent anisotropy of knitted structure. More number of fibers oriented in the wale direction and hence the stiffness and strength of Type R-W displayed higher values compared to these of Type R-C. It can be concluded that the 2.5DWK fabric reinforced composite of rigid resin is much superior to that of flexible resin from the aspect of bending properties.

The damping property of a material can be recognized to be excellent while its loss factor is superior to 0.05^{6,7)}. Recently, materials are desired with loss factor exceeding 0.1. The relation between loss factor and bending stiffness for Type R and Type F are shown in Fig.6. It can be noted that the loss factor is independent of the wale and course direction. Compared with Type F, relatively higher bending stiffness was recorded for Type R, however, the damping property is poor. On the other hand, though excellent damping property can be obtained in the case of Type F, extremely poor bending stiffness is displayed.

Fig.5 Schematic diagram of wale tested Type R bending specimen showing crack in the thickness direction.

Fig.6 Relationship between loss factor and bending stiffness of single matrix composites Type R and Type F.

From the results described above, it could be suggested that using either the rigid composite Type R or the flexible composite Type F is difficult to achieve both excellent bending and damping properties. Therefore, a hybrid matrix composite is designed which is discussed in next section.

4.2 Bending and Damping Properties of Hybrid Matrix Composites

The bending stress-displacement curves for both Type RF and Type FR in the wale and course directions are shown in Fig.7. Brittle fracture was occurred at the maximum bending stress in the course direction of both Type FR and Type RF as well as the wale direction of Type FR. However, in the case of Type RF of the wale direction, the bending load continued to increase even after a load drop (see dotted lines in Fig.7). The bending stiffness, modulus of the wale direction were higher than these of the course direction as shown in Table 2. Especially the wale direction of Type FR displayed the highest stiffness compared to the other specimens. Compared to the flexible composite, the superior bending properties can be obtained using the hybrid matrix composite.

Fig.7 Bending stress-displacement curves of Type FR and Type RF in both the course and wale direction.

Table 2 Bending properties of hybrid matrix composites.

Type	Bending Modulus (GPa)		Bending Strength (MPa)		Bending Stiffness ($\times 10^3 \text{Nm}^2$)	
	C	W	C	W	C	W
RF	0.65	1.05	33.93	—	65.51	105.81
FR	1.27	2.01	31.21	95.11	128.06	203.19

Cracks initiated on the rigid matrix at the tensile side of Type FR specimen and grew towards the boundary of the two matrixes as shown in the schematic diagram of Fig.8(a). Though a few cracks occurred along the boundary, they could not go through in the thickness direction of the specimen because the flexible resin prevented the propagation. On the other hand, cracks of Type RF specimens initiated on the compression side of the specimen and no cracks were observed at the tensile side of the flexible matrix, as shown in Fig.8(b). This may be related to the result that no final fracture occurred in the wale direction of Type RF.

Figure 9 shows the relation between loss factor and bending stiffness of Type RF and Type FR. In both Type FR and Type RF, the loss factor is higher than 0.1 in the wale direction or almost equal 0.1 in the course direction. Compared to rigid composite Type R, excellent damping properties were obtained. Especially, the hybrid matrix composite Type FR possesses not only a relatively superior bending properties but also excellent damping properties.

Fig.8 Schematic diagram of wale tested hybrid matrix composites Type FR and Type RF.
 (a) crack in the rigid resin region at tensile side of the specimen (Type FR)
 (b) crack in the rigid resin region at compressive side of the specimen (Type RF)

Fig.9 Relationship between loss factor and bending stiffness of hybrid matrix composites Type FR and Type RF.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper describes the bending and damping properties of 2.5DWK fabric reinforced composites, and -in particular- the hybrid matrix composite was discussed. The main results might be summarized as follows:

1. The 2.5DWK fabric reinforced composite are anisotropic in nature. The stiffness, modulus and strength values are higher in the wale direction compared to the course direction.
2. The single rigid matrix composite is superior to the single flexible matrix composite in bending properties but inferior in damping property.
3. The hybrid matrix composite can be tailored to possess both relatively superior bending properties and excellent damping property.

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